

Thermal Hydraulic Experiments and Code Validation for LWR SMRs within the European McSAFER Project: Overview of Activities and Current Status

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ABSTRACT

The EU Horizon 2020 project McSAFER was launched in 2020 to advance the safety research of small modular reactors (SMR) via thermal-hydraulic experiments with related code validation and numerical coupled multi-physics and multi-scale simulations. This paper provides an overview of the thermal-hydraulic experiments and code validation within the project and presents the status of these activities highlighting some of the results already obtained. Experiments are performed at three European laboratories with test facilities dedicated for the investigation of SMR-relevant phenomena. Fundamental heat transfer experiments with boiling up to critical heat flux under forced convection for rod configurations and conditions representative of SMRs are performed with the COSMOS-H facility. Performance of the helical coil steam generator, core cross flow phenomena and the general behavior of an SMR operating with natural circulation are investigated with the MOTEL facility. Heat transfer phenomena are investigated in conditions relevant for SMRs also in forced to natural circulation transients with the HWAT facility. Selected thermal hydraulic system, subchannel and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) codes are validated with the experimental data.

KEYWORDS

experiments, code validation, small modular reactors, light water reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

A multitude of different small modular reactor (SMR) designs based on different reactor technologies from thermal to fast neutron spectrum reactors designed with various coolant and other material choices and fuel types exist [1] that may challenge the available tools and experimental data used for their safety demonstration. Even for light water reactor (LWR) SMRs, the designs may feature new smaller core designs, different operating conditions and principles, such as natural circulation cooling, not only for the passive safety systems, but for the primary coolant flow during operation (see, e.g., NuScale [2] and CAREM [3]), novel components like helical coil steam generators and new containment designs [2]. Such new design features require further development, validation and demonstration of computer codes used in the safety analyses. Also, the developments in available computing capacity make it possible to replace legacy tools with more advanced high-fidelity multi-physics and multi-scale methods, such as developed in earlier European research projects like HPMC, McSAFE and NURESAFE [4], provided their applicability, validity and benefit over traditional methods can be proved.

To address the above challenges and support the deployment of SMRs in the European Union (EU), the project McSAFER (High-performance advanced methods and experimental investigations for the safety evaluation of generic small modular reactors) was launched in 2020 as a collaboration of 12 European research organizations along with participation from Argentina [5]. While this collaborative effort includes both thermal-hydraulic experiments and numerical simulation activities covering neutronics, thermal-hydraulics and fuel behaviour of different levels of fidelity and ranging from core level analyses to multi-physics/multi-scale analyses of the plant considering several different LWR SMR designs, this paper focuses on the experimental investigations and the related code validation work in the project. Three European test facilities, COSMOS-H at KIT, MOTEL at LUT and HWAT at KTH, and the related experimental campaigns are introduced, as well as the code validation work including thermal-hydraulic tools from system codes to subchannel and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) codes. The paper describes the current status of these efforts and provides a glimpse to the already obtained results and developed models.

2. MCSAFER PROJECT OVERVIEW

McSAFER is an EU Horizon 2020 project between 13 partner organizations (see Figure 1) coordinated by KIT and receiving funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2019-2020 [5]. The project, initially planned for three years, launched in September 2020 and will continue until the end of February 2024 due to a six month extension. The general aim is to advance the safety research for LWR SMRs by combining experimental and analytical investigations. This involves development and improvement of simulation tools for SMR safety evaluations, performing SMR relevant experiments and utilizing the measured data for the validation of simulation tools, as well as applying simulation tools based on traditional, advanced low-order and high-fidelity methods to four SMR designs with the aim of demonstrating the advantages of advanced tools compared to legacy methods.

The work in McSAFER is distributed into seven work packages (WPs) as illustrated in Figure 1. The scientific work is performed in the work packages from WP2 to WP5. The experimental investigations and code validation, which this paper focuses on, are performed in WP2. The WP3 considers multi-physics core analyses with coupled toolsets utilizing either traditional methods with nodal diffusion neutronics coupled with 1D thermal-hydraulic system codes, low-order neutron transport with subchannel codes, or high-fidelity Monte Carlo neutronics coupled with subchannel thermal-hydraulic and fuel thermo-mechanic codes. The WP4 focuses on multi-scale reactor pressure vessel thermal-hydraulics with system codes coupled either

with subchannel or CFD codes. The WP5 involves coupled system thermal-hydraulics, 3D nodal neutronics and subchannel or CFD level thermal hydraulics in the multi-scale/multi-physics SMR plant analyses.

Figure 1. McSAFER project partners (left) and distribution of work into seven work packages (right).

3. EXPERIMENTS WITHIN MCSAFER

Thermal hydraulic experiments within McSAFER are conducted at three European facilities: the COSMOS-H facility located in Karlsruhe, Germany and operated by KIT, the MOTEL facility located in Lappeenranta, Finland and operated by LUT, the HWAT facility located in Stockholm, Sweden and operated by KTH. The facilities and experiments have been designed for investigating thermal and flow phenomena relevant for LWR SMRs and to provide high-quality data for the validation of thermal hydraulic analysis codes. A description of each test facility and the plan of experiments is provided in the following including also highlights of already obtained results and completed activities.

3.1. Tests at the COSMOS-H facility

COSMOS-H is a thermohydraulic loop for liquid water and steam under SMR and PWR typical pressure conditions. Within McSAFER, the facility is used for flow boiling tests in fuel assemblies up to the boiling crisis.

The system achieves a maximum mass flow up to 1.4 kg/s, pressure up to 170 bar, temperature up to 360 °C with a thermal system power of approx. 1.9 MW (600 kW are available for the test section). The complete water inventory is approximately 3.5 m³. As shown in Figure 2 the facility consists of a high-pressure water and steam loop with a pump, a steam generator, a steam superheater and a condenser/cooler. The test loop also has a modular, adaptable test section and two bypasses so that the flow direction in the test section can be changed. Furthermore, the facility has a powerful cooling system and a water management system. The extensive safety system allows the use of sight glasses under full pressure and temperature conditions.

To meet the different requirements for test setups and instrumentation, a modular test section system was constructed. This makes it possible to operate different directly heated heater arrangements, such as a single tube in the annular gap or a rod bundle (Figure 3), in the same pressure envelope. Instrumentation on the test section includes numerous thermocouples in the heated tube, heater output, pressure differential and two modules with sight glasses.

Numerous subsystems of the test track and the facility have already been evaluated in the course of preliminary tests. For example, the sight glasses were examined and the reaction time for load shedding in the event of boiling crisis (DNB) at the heater was determined. The sight glasses were designed in principle for 17 MPa and 360 °C. In the tests carried out so far up to 310 °C and 10 MPa, the proof of function has already been demonstrated. Further tests will follow which will gradually approach the full test conditions.

The investigations on flow boiling in McSAFER are to be carried out up to the critical heat flux. In order to avoid damage to the heater arrangement, it is therefore necessary to be able to switch off the heating load quickly. Preliminary investigations have shown that a maximum of 0.2 s elapse between the measured temperature excursion at a thermocouple in the heater and the complete shutdown of the up to 600 kW heating power. This value should be sufficient to prevent damage to the heater assembly.

Figure 2. CAD model of the COSMOS-H facility.

Figure 3. Modular test section including high pressure windows.

3.1.1. Prepared experiments and measurement matrix

The complex phenomena of flow boiling and boiling crisis, which can be expected here in particular in the form of departure from nucleate boiling (DNB), depend on numerous parameters. The most important of these are pressure, mass flow, temperature or subcooling and heat flux. However, the heater geometry and the heater material can also have a significant influence. Therefore, the design of the test section is based as closely as possible on the real conditions in terms of material and geometry. The test conditions are also selected in such a way that, on the one hand, useful data sets are generated for modelling and validation, and, on the other hand, the development of the main variables influencing the flow and heat transfer can be observed. This results in 20 measurement conditions for each series of experiments. The boundary conditions of the planned experiments with variations in pressure, temperature and mass flow are shown in Figure 4. In each experiment, the experimental boundary conditions are then set at the plant and the heating power in the test section is gradually increased until the critical heat flux density is reached. Triggered by the locally rising temperature, the heating load is then switched off and the critical heat flux can be calculated.

Figure 4. Graphical illustration of the planned test parameters.

The facility and the test arrangement were completed in December 2022 and are being commissioned during the spring 2023. The next step are safety tests for the commissioning of the entire facility. A first series of experiments will be carried out with a test section of a single heated Zircalloy-4 tube in an annular gap. Subsequently, a bundle of five tubes will be investigated in the McSAFER Project.

3.2. Tests at the MOTEL facility

MOTEL (MOdular TEst Loop) is a multifunctional integral test facility constructed and operated at LUT University in Lappeenranta, Finland [6]. MOTEL consists of flange-connected modules that together form a pressure vessel that houses the main components of a prototypic integral PWR type SMR. These modules include the core, the steam generator and the pressurizer as shown in Figure 5. Within the McSAFER project, the MOTEL facility is used to investigate the performance of a helical coil steam generator and the core flow phenomena.

As the case with several LWR SMRs, MOTEL includes a steam generator of helical coil design with a total of 16 tubes divided into four groups with separate hot and cold collectors. The secondary side water flows in the tube side while the primary side coolant flows in the shell side. Above the steam generator is a pressurizer module that has a heater element. The facility operates at natural circulation such that the coolant

Figure 5. Modular design of MOTEL.

enters the core at the bottom, rises through a central riser tube above the steam generator, turns around to enter the annular downcomer space that is between the riser tube and the pressure vessel, flows downwards through the steam generator located in the top part of the downcomer and falls back to the bottom of the core via the downcomer space that ends near the core inlet at the bottom to let water enter the core. The core of MOTEL has a relatively large diameter and consists of 132 heater rods, 145 dummy rods and 16 instrumentation rods. The full height of the facility is 7.4 m, the diameter is 711 mm and the maximum heating power 1000 kW. The facility can operate with a pressure of 40 bar and a temperature of 250 °C.

3.2.1. MOTEL Experiments and Test Matrix

The experiments conducted with MOTEL within the McSAFER project have been divided into two parts; the first set of experiments focuses on the behavior of the steam generator and the second set on the core flow phenomena. While both experiments provide practically data from all the instrumentation installed in the facility, the steam generator experiments are intended to provide validation data especially for validating system thermal hydraulic and CFD codes, while the core-focused experiments are intended for subchannel and CFD code validation.

The steam generator experiments have been planned to consist of two test series which both attempt to achieve a, more or less, steady state behavior at different core power levels. One series considers low core heating powers of 75 kW, 100 kW, 125 kW and 150 kW, while another series investigates the steam generator behaviour at power levels of 250 kW, 500 kW, 750 kW and 1000 kW. Both test series consist of initial heating up and pressurisation of the facility (35 bar primary, 10 bar secondary) and the power steps, each 1 h in duration. The experiments provide information of the behaviour of the helical coil steam generator within the natural circulation facility via thermo-couple measurements that have been installed both shell side (primary) and inside the tubes (secondary) of the steam generator. On both sides, there are

measurements at five different elevations so that the total number of measurements in the primary side is 10 and on the secondary side 80, as each steam generator tube has five measurements.

The core flow phenomena experiments utilize the MOTEL design feature that allows to impose different radial core power distributions. As shown in Figure 6, the electrically heated rods of the MOTEL core have been distributed into 12 groups in which the power can be individually controlled. This way, different radial power distributions and asymmetries can be imposed to potentially induce cross flows and temperature distributions that could be detected with the core instrumentation.

Figure 6. MOTEL core before its installation to the facility (left) and the core heating segments (right). Each colored square in the segment map contains one heater rod while the white positions contain an instrument rod. There are also unheated dummy rods in between the heater and measurement rods.

The core has 132 temperature measurements in the heater rods and 80 fluid temperature measurements inside separate hollow instrument rods through which the coolant can flow. The instrument rod positions are shown in Figure 6 and each instrument rod contains five measurements at different elevations. As in the heat exchanger experiments, the core flow experiments were divided into two series of experiments. The first series considers asymmetric power distributions where different powers are imposed in the two halves of the core as well as a case where only two heating segments are powered. The second series divides the core into two or three rings for which different powers are used. A total of seven different radial power distributions are examined along with uniform power distributions in between the runs.

3.2.2. Status of Experiments and Obtained Results

The MOTEL experiments within McSAFER have progressed as planned without major delays as the facility was operational already in the early phase of the project. The experiments focusing on the heat exchanger behavior were completed and the experimental data processed by the end of 2021. The core flow phenomena experiments and data analysis were completed by the end of 2022. The heat exchanger experiments revealed that with the operating conditions used in the experiments, the lower heating power levels up to 250 kW did not yet result in significant superheating of steam except occasionally in some individual tubes, while more pronounced superheating was observed at powers above 250 kW. However, the steam generator showed unstable behavior at these higher power levels observed as strongly oscillating temperatures as shown in

Figure 7. The core cross flow experiments revealed that to observe even minor differences in temperatures between the measurement rods requires rather extreme power distributions with the current MOTEL core design and the used total core power. The core power in these experiments was limited to 250 kW considering it as the highest heating power that showed stable behaviour in the steam generator tests. An example of the coolant axial temperature distributions measured in the measurement rods for the test with heating only in two heating segments is shown in Figure 7. Data from both experiments should provide interesting, yet challenging validation cases for thermal-hydraulic codes.

Figure 7. Results from the MOTEL steam generator (left) and core cross flow (right) experiments. The steam generator experiments at four different power levels show oscillatory superheating at powers of 500 kW, 750 kW and 1000 kW. The core cross flow experiments with heating power on in only two heating segments show temperature difference between the heated and unheated regions as well as slight temperature increase in the measurements located near the heated regions.

3.3. Tests at the HWAT Facility

HWAT is a high-temperature high-pressure water loop designed for the investigation of two-phase flows. Within the McSAFER project the facility is used to investigate heat transfer phenomena, such as CHF and DNB, in SMR relevant conditions both in forced and natural circulation as well as in forced to natural circulation transients. The HWAT experiments aim to provide data for the validation of thermal-hydraulic codes and reduction of modelling uncertainty on heat transfer up to the critical heat flux, the effect of transient pressure on the flow stability in natural circulation, power void reactivity feedback, and non-linear power profile in flow regimes and conditions typical for SMRs with the focus on the transition from forced to natural circulation.

The facility is capable of operating at up to 2 kg/s flow rate, 250 bar pressure, 450 °C temperature and 1 MW heating power. Two series of experiments will be performed with HWAT within McSAFER and the initial facility used in the first test series will be modified for the second series. An open secondary loop is used to cool down the condenser. The effective height of the loop in both configurations is 8.9 m. As instrumentation, in addition to thermocouples, pressure transducers and flow meters in various parts of the facility, HWAT features a multi-sensor probe at the exit of the heated riser which will provide unique measurements of local flow characteristics including dynamic pressure, void fraction / bubble size distribution

and temperature (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. HWAT setup for the first (left) and second (middle) test series and the multi-sensor probe unit (right).

The first test series consists of forced circulation steady-state tests including commissioning and model input calibration tests as well as investigation of distributions of the flow characteristics with the multi-sensor probe and heat transfer in different flow conditions inside the heated riser. In the first tests, the facility consists of an electrically heated test section (heated riser), a condenser, a reheater and a pump (see Figure 8). The objective of the first series of tests is to measure heat transfer, flow regime, void fraction and local flow velocity in steady state forced circulation conditions including CHF and possibly post dryout.

The second series investigates forced to natural circulation transients and includes tests for model input calibration and validation, natural circulation stability tests and investigations on local transient flow characteristics both for forced and natural circulation. For the second test series another loop is included in between the two existing ones. It is connected to the primary loop via a steam generator of helical coil or tube-and-shell design. The primary loop models the primary system of an SMR (in vessel circulation). It accommodates a heated section in the riser and a heat exchanger in the downcomer. The secondary loop represents either the feedwater / steam line systems or the residual passive heat removal system connected to a pool type condenser. The tertiary loop serves as an open water recovery system for the condenser. The primary and secondary loop can operate in forced and natural circulation flow. The goal of the second test series is to provide data for code development and validation during transition from forced to natural circulation in the primary and secondary loops. The selected heat and mass fluxes, temperatures and pressure are characteristic for SMRs.

3.3.1. Status of Experiments

The HWAT facility has been prepared for the tests during the project. The commissioning tests are ongoing and first experimental results are expected in the spring 2023. There has been some delay in commissioning

the facility due to delivery problems caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The waiting time has, on the other hand, allowed extensive design and pre-test analyses to be conducted for both test series in the mean time.

So far, various radial profiles of fluid velocity and temperature were measured under single phase flow conditions at the outlet of the heated riser using the multi-sensor unit equipped with a Pitot tube and a TC. These profiles can be compared to well-known profile of fully developed turbulent flow and 2D simulations. Example of such comparison is shown in Figure 9. The Von Karman velocity profile for turbulent flow was used for comparison, in addition to the velocity and temperature profiles simulated by a 2D model [7]. In the presented comparisons, the measurement and predictions of fluid velocity and temperature radial profiles match very well.

Figure 9. Radial profiles of fluid velocity (left) and temperature (right).

4. CODE VALIDATION WITHIN MCSAFER

The results obtained from the McSAFER experiments are used for code validation. The validation considers three categories of thermal hydraulic codes including CFD, subchannel and system codes. The validation work is done in several McSAFER partner organisations and involves multiple codes of each category. Not all codes are validated against all experiments but partners utilize codes and experimental data based on their own needs and interests. The following provides an overview of the code validation activities highlighting some already obtained results.

4.1. CFD Code Validation

CFD codes validated within the project include ANSYS CFX and Fluent as well as OpenFOAM. Data from each of the three experimental facilities are utilized and altogether four partners perform CFD analyses.

The COSMOS-H experiments are simulated with CFX by KIT and UJV and with OpenFOAM by LUT. As data from the COSMOS-H experiments is still pending, the CFD analysis work has focused on preparation of the models and preliminary calculations based on the already defined test matrices. KIT has performed CFD analyses in support of the experiments, such as investigating the inlet and outlet conditions of the test facility, confirming the expected functioning of a flow straightener design to be installed to the flow entrance of the test section (see Figure 10). In addition, UJV and LUT have been preparing their own CFD models for the simulation of the first COSMOS-H tests to be performed for a single heated rod geometry.

Figure 10. CFX simulation results for the inlet region of the COSMOS-H test section (left) and the CFD mesh for the spacer structure of the MOTEL core (right) by KIT.

The MOTEL experiments are simulated with CFX by KIT and with Fluent by UJV. The KIT simulations focus on the core flow behavior related experiments for which a detailed model of the MOTEL core including the spacer constructs (see Figure 10) is being developed. The CFD simulations are expected to utilize shear stress transport (SST) turbulence modelling and the finalized model is estimated to consist of around 250 million unstructured mesh elements with $y^+ \approx 1$ for the heated structures. The detailed CFD modeling of the core is expected to complement the interpretation of the core flow phenomena as the data obtained from the experiments is limited to thermocouple measurements only. The Fluent calculations of MOTEL performed by UJV, on the other hand, focus on the steam generator experiments. As these simulations involving natural circulation flow necessitate the inclusion of basically the whole primary circuit, the UJV approach is to include the core and the steam generator as porous zones with momentum losses and heat sources/sinks defined based on data from experiments. The model of the full primary side in the Fluent model thus consists of reasonable 1.57 million mesh cells. UJV has already completed the CFD analysis of all steam generator experiments. The results show good agreement with measured ones regarding axial temperature distributions in the heating power range from 250 kW to 1000 kW as can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Fluent simulation results of the MOTEL steam generator experiment by UJV including the temperature and velocity contours (left) and the comparison of primary side axial temperature profiles between the experiments and the Fluent simulations (right).

The HWAT experiments are simulated with OpenFOAM by KTH. As the first experiments are still pending the CFD work has so far focused on supporting simulations to support the design of the facility, its components and the test matrices.

4.2. Subchannel Code Validation

Subchannel code validation in McSAFER considers the codes SUBCHANFLOW, VIPRE and CTF. The subchannel code validation utilizes data from the COSMOS-H experiments, especially the ones involving multiple heated rods, and the MOTEL core flow focused experiments. A total of three partners are involved with the subchannel code validation.

Thus far, as the subchannel code validation requires data from the last sets of experiments which are either yet to be conducted or have just been finalized, the work with subchannel codes has focused on development of inputs based on the available data of the facilities and the defined test matrices. The COSMOS-H experiments will be utilized for the validation of the SUBCHANFLOW by KIT and VIPRE by UJV. The MOTEL experiments will be calculated by UJV with VIPRE and by TBL with CTF. Thus far, TBL has prepared a CTF model consisting of 148 subchannels and 20 axial divisions that include the 132 heated rods, the 16 measurement rods, the 145 dummy rods and the 2 support grids of the facility and performed preliminary analyses against measured data from the test runs performed with MOTEL (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. CTF model of the MOTEL core (left) and preliminary calculation results (right) by TBL.

4.3. System Code Validation

System code validation in McSAFER involves data from all the three experiment facilities and the codes TRACE, APROS, RELAP5-3D and GOTHIC. System code analyses are performed by five project partners.

The COSMOS-H experiments are simulated by KIT with TRACE and by UJV with RELAP5-3D. KIT has already prepared a TRACE model for the COSMOS-H experiments and tested models for pre-test simulations. Similarly, UJV has finalized the RELAP5-3D model of the facility (see Figure 13).

The MOTEL experiments are simulated by LUT with APROS and by UPM with TRACE. LUT has developed two APROS models of the MOTEL facility; a simplified and a detailed one. The main difference

between the models is, that the steam generator is represented by a single average heat transfer tube in the simplified model, while the detailed model includes each of the 16 steam generator tubes. First simulations show that the models are capable replicating the facility behaviour during the steam generator tests with reasonable accuracy as can be seen in Figure 13. In addition, as the MOTEL facility closely resembles the NuScale SMR design, UPM is in the process of adapting an existing TRACE model of the NuScale SMR to represent the MOTEL facility for their simulations.

Figure 13. The RELAP5-3D model of the COSMOS-H prepared by UJV (left) and preliminary APROS results obtained by LUT of the MOTEL experiments compared to experimental data (right).

The HWAT experiments are simulated by UPM with TRACE and by KTH with GOTHIC and TRACE. Both UPM and KTH have prepared system code models (see Figure 14) and performed pre-test simulations of the planned tests according to the established test matrices.

Figure 14. TRACE model of the HWAT facility prepared by UPM.

5. SUMMARY

The McSAFER project was launched in the autumn 2020 for experimental and numerical investigations of LWR SMRs. The project includes a work package dedicated to thermal hydraulic experiments and code validation to support the safety analyses of SMRs. Experiments are conducted at the COSMOS-H, MOTEL and HWAT facilities addressing SMR-relevant flow and heat transfer phenomena. System, subchannel and CFD level thermal-hydraulic codes are validated using the data measured from the experiments. The experiments with the MOTEL facility investigating the behaviour of a helical coil steam generator and core cross flow phenomena have been finished and the data is already used for code validation. Experiments with the COSMOS-H facility will investigate heat transfer between rod and coolant up to CHF for single rod and rod bundle configurations. Experiments with the HWAT loop will investigate thermal and flow phenomena in forced and natural circulation, as well as transition from forced to natural circulation. Both of these experiments are expected to produce first results during spring 2023. The code validation is progressing with the development of the calculation models of the experiments and pre-test simulations. Some of the validation activities have already produced first results. Both, the experiments and code validation work performed in McSAFER should prove valuable for supporting the future deployment of LWR SMRs in Europe and world-wide.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2019-2020 under grant agreement No 945063. The content of this paper reflects only the authors' views and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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